

THE CONFLICT BETWEEN MOROCCO AND THE POLISARIO OVER THE WESTERN SAHARA

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Abstract

This study focuses on examining the Moroccan conflict with the Polisario over Western Sahara, in the absence of a settlement and commitment to a ceasefire. The study proposes a draft peace agreement between Morocco and the Polisario, especially after 50 years of conflict and 8 years of proposals without reaching a political solution that satisfies the parties. By using a descriptive-analytical approach with models and methodological tools, the conflict was analyzed from different perspectives. What the study presents is the result of the optimal solution for resolving the conflict, which is expanded autonomy, and reaching a common ground that eliminates or reduces the disparities between the conflicting parties.

Keywords: Conflict, Morocco, The Polisario, Western Sahara.

INTRODUCTION

The Western Sahara issue is one of the oldest conflicts in Africa. A solution seems difficult whether it is bilateral, Arab, or international, as the United Nations considers it a disputed territory between Morocco and the Polisario.

Western Sahara is a former Spanish colony, inhabited by less than one million people, and most of its territory has been under Moroccan control since the 1970s. Morocco has proposed a plan to grant the region autonomy under the sovereignty of Morocco (Abu Fakhir,2009).

However, **The Polisario** rejected this plan with the support of Algeria, and demanded a referendum that guarantees the right to self-determination, in light of the failure of UN mediation efforts (Boudra,2005).

After the independence of the Maghreb countries, the colonial conflict over Western Sahara turned into a regional dispute between Morocco, Mauritania, Algeria, and the Polisario, which declared the establishment of the Sahrawi Arab Democratic Republic on February 27, 1976. In 1998, the United Nations proposed a referendum for the people of Western Sahara on self-determination, but it was not implemented due to renewed disagreements raised by both disputing parties, particularly concerning issues of identity and population census, which obstructed the implementation of the UN plan. This issue is still listed under Chapter VI of the United Nations Charter, which makes its decisions non-binding for its members (Al-Bayati, 2012)

Western Sahara has been the cause of strained international relations between Morocco and many countries that voted in favor of Western Sahara or recognized the Sahrawi Arab Democratic Republic. It was also the reason for Morocco's withdrawal from the Organization of African Unity and the severing of diplomatic relations with many African countries.

Additionally, Morocco has engaged in ongoing conflicts with Algeria due to its position on the issue, and Morocco's relations with many countries around the world are now determined based on their stance on the Western Sahara issue (Al-Hamdani,2013).

Statement of Purpose

The research problem lies in the absence of a genuine settlement that satisfies both parties through a peace agreement that guarantees each side's basic needs.

Significance of the Study

The significance of this research lies in its departure from the conventional approaches used in writings on the Western Sahara conflict between Morocco and the Polisario Front. It analyzes the causes and motivations behind the ongoing crisis to reach a settlement between the parties, especially in light of the failure of existing proposals: the option of Western Sahara joining Morocco, which was rejected by the Polisario; the option of full independence, which was rejected by Morocco; the rejection of the so-called "third option" by the Polisario and Algeria; and the failure of the fourth proposal made by Kofi Annan in 2002, suggesting a two-thirds share for Morocco and one-third for the Polisario, which Morocco rejected, accusing Algeria of harboring regional ambitions.

Study Objectives

The main objective of the study is to analyze the stages and development of the conflict, along with the main motives behind its emergence and the factors contributing to its persistence, particularly in the absence of a settlement and under the ongoing ceasefire between the two parties, and develop a proposed peace agreement between the parties and evaluate its potential success or failure based on countervailing forces.

Hypothesis of the study

- The bilateral solution is limited between Morocco and the Polisario, and behind it Algeria to resolve the conflict.
- The difficulty of reaching a settlement due to the size of the differences between Morocco's proposal and what the Polisario wants.
- Autonomy is the best solution to resolve the conflict.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive analytical approach has been adopted to conduct the research, through the use of methodological tools, which are conflict analysis models and reach results through which it is possible to reach the settlement of the conflict between the parties.

Firstly: The description of the Western Sahara

The Western Sahara is located in the northwest of Africa, bordered to the north by Morocco, the west by the Atlantic Ocean, the south by Mauritania and the east by Algeria. It has an area of 266 thousand square kilometers, and its coastline is 1066 km long, and its land borders are

2045 kilometers. Of which 475 kilometers are shared with the rest of Morocco. And a kilometer shared with Mauritania and 50 kilometers with Algeria (Hamza,2011).

It consists geographically of two regions, Saqiya Al-Hamra in the north and extends from the city of Laayoune towards the city of Samara to the border with Algeria and the Wadi Al-Dhahab region to the south extending from the city of Boujdour to the Mauritanian border to the south (Al-Wadi, 2013).

Western Sahara consists of three administrative regions:

- Samara area, with an area of (56) thousand square kilometers.
- Laayne area, with an area of (26) thousand square kilometers.
- Dakhla area, with an area of (1840) thousand km.
- As for the geographical division, there are two parts (Saqiya Al-Hamra, Wadi Al-Dhahab) (Saleh, 2012).

Western Sahara is on the United Nations list of Non-Self-Governing Territories. In 1975, the Polisario announced the establishment of the Sahrawi Arab Democratic Republic unilaterally. Currently, the number of countries that still recognize the Polisario Front is only 34 countries, most of which are located in the African and American continents, including Angola, Namibia, South Africa, Nigeria, Mali, Mauritania, Libya, Syria, Algeria, Iran, Bolivia and Mexico (Abu Fakhr,2009).

The 46 countries, including India, Madagascar, Colombia, Chad, Paraguay, Zambia, Burkina Faso, Burkina Faso and other countries in the world, withdrawn, frozen or suspended their recognition of the secessionist Frente POLISARIO appear to be constantly growing (Hamza,2011).

It is noted that most of the countries that recognized it were in the period of the 1970s, a period of time that was characterized by the glow of demands for separation and self-determination, and the rise of the shares of socialism and leftist currents in the world, while the spark of retreats from the recognition of the Front since the 1990s, and its pace rose by the third millennium (Al-Hayali,2007).

Around 80% of the territory is subject to Moroccan sovereignty and 20% of the buffer military zone to the Mauritanian border. The Polisario Front considers the buffer zone to be liberated areas from the territory and the areas under Moroccan sovereignty are occupied areas of Morocco. The Polisario declared a state in a territory it does not control. The headquarters of the Polisario is located in Tindouf in southwestern Algeria (Khurshid,2007).

Secondly: The geography of the earth, water sources and climate

There are no permanent collapses in the Sahara region, and due to the limited water resources, agriculture in the region meets the needs of the population only, and the nomad remains the basis of life in the Western Sahara region, characterized by its climate with high heat and drought (Al-Hayali, 2007).

Thirdly: The Strategic Importance of the Western Sahara

It holds special strategic importance as the Arab Maghreb touches at both ends the most important international waterways: the Suez Canal on one side and the Strait of Gibraltar on the other, both being vital and important entrances to the Mediterranean Sea (Al-Bayati, 2012).

It represents the farthest extent of the Arabian deserts and serves as a connection point between Africa and the Arabs, with the desert's borders with neighboring countries extending two thousand kilometers, thus making it the gateway to West Africa, and it had direct connection with European colonies in the African continent previously (Abu Fakhr,2009).

As for its importance at the regional level, it is represented by its location between Morocco, Algeria and Mauritania, where it constitutes a natural depth and extension for each of them (Al-Hayali,2007).

From an economic perspective, phosphates are considered the main resource of the Western Sahara region, discovered by a Spanish researcher in 1947. There are reserves of gas and oil in the coasts of Western Sahara, Morocco signed agreements for oil exploration with some companies in 2001, the most important of which were with the French company TotalFinaElf and the American company Kerr-McGee Corp. The Polisario objected to this, but Morocco resorted to the United Nations and was permitted to explore on the condition that oil not be exploited commercially without the consent of the local population (Diab,2005).

The iron reserves amount in this area to approximately 700,000 tons, and uranium is found in the city of Smara. Livestock is one of the most important resources that provide a livelihood for the population, and the Saharan coasts are rich in fish resources, as its coasts are considered the richest fishing grounds and the most important fishing center in the city of Laayoune (Al-Wadi, 2013).

Although it possesses tourism potential but lacks infrastructure such as hotels, resorts, and recreational ports. The trade sector is one of the main attractions, and the city of Laayoune is a major commercial center with a population of 136.7 thousand, but in terms of health and educational services, they are very limited (Alrawi,2010).

The stages of conflict development illustrate the pre-conflict stage "Pre-conflict," which is the period leading up to the conflict; the escalation stage "Confrontation," such as confrontations, violence, polarizations, and the emergence of symbolic figures for each party and divergence; the crisis or war stage "Crisis"; the ceasefire stage "Outcome" and signing a peace agreement; and finally, the peace guarantees achieved "Post-conflict" through normalization of relations, reconciliation, cooperation, and partnership that represent a guarantee for the peace agreement (Sayed,2002).

Fourthly: Stages of the conflict

The fundamental stage in the conflict resolution process is analyzing how it occurs and identifying its causes. The conflict between Morocco and the Polisario will be analyzed based on the premise that thought precedes behavior, and thus it is impossible to act within the

existing conflict without understanding the reasons and motives, after which steps can be taken to reach a settlement and bring the parties together on a common ground (Al-Bayati,2012).

Using the Conflict Mapping Model, Conflict Analysis can be identified as the parties to the conflict, the weight and size of each party in the conflict, and the nature of the relationship between the parties. It will be analyzed as follows:

Morocco: Holds significant influence in the conflict and controls the larger part of Western Sahara, demanding its annexation. It fears any referendum on self-determination that does not comply with its conditions, as it could lead to the loss of a region rich in phosphates and fish resources (Al-Hamdani,2013).

For Morocco, it is an existential issue with no room for negotiation over its sovereignty and territorial integrity. Consequently, Moroccan-Algerian relations are severed, and Morocco holds Algeria responsible for the instability and tension in the region, as it is a key party to the conflict. It can be said that Morocco's stance is based on the idea of "Moroccan Sahara," which, in their view, signifies the unity of Moroccan territory (Security Council, 2015).

Polisario: Opposes Morocco and asserts its right to sovereignty. Despite reduced Algerian support due to economic and security instability in Algeria and the movement's political decline, it has moved toward accepting the UN-approved referendum to advance the issue. To demonstrate goodwill, it released 1,435 Moroccan prisoners held between 1975-2003, and sought to distance itself from terrorism in its political and military activities (Boudraa, 2005).

As for **Algeria**, it has been a primary and traditional supporter of the Polisario since its inception. Its stance is political and ideological, advocating for Polisario's independence to secure a passage through the Sahara for transporting iron from the Tindouf region to the Atlantic Ocean (Diab, 2005).

For **Mauritania:** Its principle in the Western Sahara conflict is based on preserving its borders and ensuring internal stability. Mauritania practically and officially withdrew from the conflict after signing an agreement with the Polisario in 1979, ending the state of war between them and leading to Mauritania's withdrawal from Oued Ed-Dahab and its handover to the Sahrawis (Al-Wadi, 2013).

As a former colonizer with tense relations with Morocco, **Spain** does not want the ongoing conflict to end, as it would prevent Morocco from claiming the cities of Ceuta and Melilla.

United Nations: Since 1991, it has sought a final solution to the conflict but has not succeeded because major powers have not prioritized it on the international agenda. The UN has handled the file by maintaining a balance between Morocco and Algeria, as establishing a Polisario state would threaten Morocco's security and sovereignty, while Polisario's integration into Morocco would pose a dilemma for Algeria (Sayed,2002).

The personal envoys of the Secretary-General have worked to reconcile various proposals, most notably former U.S. Secretary of State James Baker, current U.S. diplomat Christopher Ross, and Dutch diplomat Peter van Walsum, encouraging the parties to resolve the conflict and accept the autonomy proposal presented by Morocco in 2007 (Al-Bayati, 2012).

The Polisario proposed a plan aimed at independence while fully preserving Morocco's interests in the Sahara. This led to the emergence of the "Friends of Western Sahara" group, consisting of the U.S., UK, Russia, France, and Spain, pushing for a resolution and settlement between the parties (Alrawi,2010).

African Union: It has no effective role, and its members are divided due to its recognition of the Sahrawi Republic as a member. The organizational weakness of regional organizations continues to limit their role in the conflict (Al-Rawi, 2010).

From the above, we conclude that the conflict map highlights Algeria's role as a key to resolving the conflict. Other countries that could act as mediators or participate in negotiations depend on current relationship networks and specific timing, as relationships naturally shift due to international circumstances and evolving interests (Sayed, 2002).

Using the ABC Tringle Model of the Galtung Triangle for Conflict Analysis, we Look at Conflict Through Three Dimensions: “Attitudes, Behavior and Structural Contradictions”. Which Can Put Us on The Justifications of Behavior For each of The Parties to the Conflict.

The first party: the Moroccan government

Morocco justifies the intervention of its army against the Polisario, the extermination operations against Sahrawis, arrests, and pursuit through Morocco's general trend of perceiving a threat to national unity and concern for its territorial integrity, as well as countering external interventions supported by foreign parties aimed at promoting the separation of Moroccan interior and increasing its weakness.

On the other hand, the Polisario views their repeated attacks and guerrilla warfare as stemming from their feeling of deprivation of the right to self-determination, lack of security, and denial of an independent Sahrawi identity, resulting from policies adopted by the Moroccan government, including marginalization, repression, expansion at the expense of others, and the strategy of building walls, which indicates a policy of discrimination, in addition to poor health and educational services (Sayed,2002).

We conclude from the above that there is an environment full of differences due to each party's concept of sovereignty and the nature of isolated tribal communities within, in addition to the implementation of certain policies such as pressure on refugees and the strategy of building walls—all factors that contributed to and justified the explosion of the situation, leading to kidnapping operations, guerrilla warfare, and the Moroccan army's intervention in response (Saleh,2012).

However, the Western side of the sand wall still benefits from significant Moroccan investments and improvements in infrastructure and facilities in Boujdour and Dakhla. Despite some protests during the extension period of the UN mission report, they were confronted and dispersed by Moroccan security within the administration of the southern provinces (Shafi'a,2009).

The Secretary-General of the Polisario points to human rights violations west of the wall, the illegal exploitation of natural resources, and the inappropriate use of force, demanding the release of all political prisoners of Western Sahara.

On the Eastern side of the wall, the increase in civilian activities and infrastructure construction in six villages reflects the implementation of the Sahrawi National Council's program to consolidate the exercise of sovereignty in the liberated territories (Security Council, 2015).

Morocco, the Polisario, and Algeria bear the primary responsibility for the security of UN civilian and military personnel in their respective mission sites, indicating the increasing cost of the conflict for the three aforementioned parties—a cost they cannot bear under the prevailing political conditions. This suggests the possibility of a peace agreement that brings the parties together to reach a solution that ensures the needs and interests of each party (Shafi'a,2009).

Conflict Analysis Using the Tree Model. The tree model contributes to understanding conflicts and their causes, thus helping to reach an appropriate solution that addresses the root causes of the conflict and prevents its recurrence. For example, when examining hostile relations or ancient history between two parties in depth, it tends to analyze and identify issues through specialized task forces to understand the depth of the conflict (Shaalaa,2011).

It is a model that benefits the parties that enter the negotiation process by relying on the analysis of the onion and its levels into three levels: the declared positions, which are the demands in which a party expresses the highest ceiling of what it wants to achieve from the negotiation process, the second level, the positions or interests that it really wants, and here it is possible to waive something that was requested in the declared positions to achieve any successful settlement, the minimum of these demands and interests must be achieved, and the last level is what the parties need, i.e. the basic needs that there is no settlement without or in case of abandonment (Saleh,2012).

Fifthly: Conflict Resolution Phase

When understanding the demands of both conflict parties, we move toward a peace agreement as a guarantee for resolution. Here, we must identify the actual field forces driving the conflict and those opposing it.

The field force analysis model, or the "reverse tension" model, helps identify the parties involved in the field and determine their level of influence. When an agreement is signed between the two parties, this model highlights who supports implementing the agreement and who opposes it. No resolution can be achieved without understanding the strength of the parties and the obstructive elements (Al-Hamdani,2013).

If the forces supporting the signing of a resolution agreement are stronger than the opposing forces, the agreement succeeds. However, if the opposing forces are stronger, the agreement fails. It is crucial to develop a strategy to shift positions and transform opposing forces into supportive ones—this is where success lies.

The situation in Western Sahara is generally calm, with the ceasefire still in place under the presence of MINURSO, the UN mission, and the International Committee of the Red Cross as a neutral mediator working with concerned families to investigate the fate of those still missing. After 50 years of conflict, how can the continuation of the status quo and the lack of engagement in building and innovating solutions be justified? (Security Council, 2015).

Decentralization is a tool used to alter spatial planning policies. It is a process aimed at transferring economic and service activities from a dominant central region to less developed regions through municipalities, regional councils, and public institutions—granting a degree of autonomy in internal affairs but under the supervision and control of the central authority (Shaalán,2011).

However, there are levels of decentralization, and here we need the level of concession—meaning a locally autonomous government. For conflict resolution, we do not need the level of delegation (service and administrative responsibilities), deconcentrating, or abstraction.

A peace agreement has been reached between the parties to the conflict in the form of expanded autonomy, where autonomy provides an honorable exit for both the Polisario and Algeria in light of the increasing threats in the region and the instability that creates an environment filled with frustration and despair, driving youth in the Tindouf camps to join terrorist groups. This will push Algeria and neighboring countries to strengthen opportunities to find a solution (Shaalán,2011).

Algeria is the key to the solution as it plays with all available cards, including the card of Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb, which drives Algeria to gradually become the Pakistan of North Africa in its relations with Al-Qaeda, and in turn, turning Mauritania, Mali, and Niger into small Afghan-like regions in the Sahel (Al-Hamdani,2013).

In light of these positions and changes, the Polisario movement, which found itself in an unenviable situation, had to retreat from its fundamental stance advocating for the independence of the Sahara. In order to avoid being included in the terrorism list, it accepted the principle of a referendum for the Sahrawi people and released a group of Moroccan prisoners as a goodwill gesture to distance itself from the label of terrorism in its military and political activities.

There is concern about the possibility of a coup against the Polisario in light of an aging and stagnant leadership, the decline in Algerian financial support which is burdening the Algerian treasury, and the increasing international isolation of the front (Saleh,2012).

As for the friendly countries of Western Sahara, such as “Russia, Spain, Britain, the United States, and France,” Spain continues to facilitate the work of the UN envoy to the Sahara region by providing a Spanish Air Force plane to facilitate his movements in North Africa (UN Security Council, 2015).

Russia calls for a solution to the Western Sahara issue because they have been involved in the United Nations mission stationed there from the beginning and are the largest in number.

France: The second international power with a presence in the crisis for several reasons, including its relations with Morocco, its relations with Algeria, the background of these relations, and its role in the African context. France also highlights the region's suffering from increasing instability and the active presence of Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb in the Sahel region.

The justification for the great powers' desire and push for a peace agreement is that if Algeria and the Polisario continue to reject the Moroccan proposal, a return to military confrontations between the two parties is likely, but costly for both sides. This would push the great powers to intervene to find a solution, fearing that the region could become a breeding ground for terrorist groups like ISIS, turning it into a place to settle accounts with the West (Mahaba,1999).

However, this force may be confronted by another power, Israel, which has no interest in resolving the conflict. Israel aims to divide and fragment the region to maintain its national security, driven by concerns over survival and existence. This was highlighted in Bernard Lewis's study titled "Bernard Lewis and the Project for the Division of the Middle East: Past and Present (Iraq as a Model)," where he was among the first to advocate for dividing the Middle East from Pakistan to the Maghreb, a topic raised on the eve of the establishment of the State of Israel on Palestinian land in 1948 (Al-Hamdani,2013).

Neighboring African countries such as Guinea, Gabon, Burkina Faso, the Comoros, and the Democratic Republic of the Congo also support the agreement. Mauritanian President Mohamed Ould Abdel Aziz affirms that Mauritania's position is one of positive neutrality and highlights negative consequences, such as the drug trade passing through Mauritania to Mali. This phenomenon poses a severe security threat to all the countries in the Sahel and Sahara region as it contributes to financing terrorist and extremist criminal groups.

Fearing the spread of more extremist groups that trade in drugs and weapons and move between their countries, these groups have become a force of opposition, taking advantage of the unresolved conflict to gain more financial profit from illegal trade. If a solution and settlement are reached, it is inevitable that mechanisms will be put in place to restrain and limit them, leading to their eventual disappearance.

Senegal supports the solution of autonomy, saying: "It is the only new and positive dynamic that offers the best prospects for a political and final solution acceptable to all". Meanwhile, Gabon emphasizes the necessity and urgency of reaching a final solution, stating that there are repercussions from the risks of instability and other criminal activities in the region (Saleh,2012).

Burkina Faso confirms that autonomy is the appropriate solution, through diplomat Michel Kafedendo, who states that leaving the status quo as it is is unsustainable and does not serve any of the parties involved in the issue. This situation is fraught with risks that threaten peace and stability in the region.

Through the interest ceiling in negotiations for Morocco, it is autonomy, and for the Polisario, it is the referendum mechanism. We will look for a convergence between them through expanded autonomy. Based on the change of directions among the parties in the triangle model and the resolution of contradictions from each side's perspective towards the other, in the end, there will be no behavior, as the solution will address the part related to structural contradictions and directions, which is the driving force behind the continuity of the conflict. This is unlike the option of a ceasefire, which represents "negative peace." What we are always seeking is positive peace (Al-Hamdani,2013).

Sixthly: A proposed Expanded Autonomy Peace Agreement between the Two Parties to the Conflict: "Formation of a Federal Government":

- Formation of geographical units in southern regions according to the constitution to ensure strong decentralization.
- Administrative units should have autonomy in establishing their internal systems and should not be required to have the government set the general framework for the local authorities or impose it themselves.
- It should provide a governmental institutional structure with an independent parliament and judiciary, without exceptions for certain institutions, such as the judiciary.
- Officials should be appointed through elections by the population.
- The powers of the administrative units should be determined according to the constitution, not through laws or administrative decisions.
- They should have full legislative authority and the right to collect taxes in areas where they exercise their powers and independence in spending.
- Local and regional interests should be represented at the national level by parliamentary institutions, not by individuals.
- The central authority in the state cannot delegate all of its powers and concentrate them in higher administration, otherwise, the result would be a cessation of its operations.
- Autonomy is characterized by wide-ranging powers and independence through the tasks it performs under the sovereignty of the state through the state's concession.
- Local councils have powers through the central government's concession of some of its legislative, judicial, and executive powers in favor of the Polisario group to perform its tasks in a specific geographic region.
- The justification for choosing expanded autonomy under Moroccan sovereignty is "the reunification of a state that had its regions fragmented and its independence undermined by colonial powers. Adopting autonomy makes reunification easier. Autonomy is a miniature system of general governance of the state, and if it operates within a democratic framework, it maintains its cohesion."

But why has autonomy remained at the proposal and initiative level, and is it possible to implement this principle without supporting institutional structures?

Atrakine mentions that autonomy excludes the option of secession by establishing mechanisms for coexistence between the parties based on the data of the conflict and the relationship of the parties (Atrakine, 2007).

Local governance will remain part of the initiative as long as it is not placed within the framework of an integrated political project based on a legitimate system that addresses the issue of Western Sahara. This proposal requires the existence of operational elites who support a unification project and are capable of implementing it (Al-Hamdani,2013).

Historical readings show that Morocco has created elites with natural extensions, sometimes from tribes that have no influence in the Sahrawi social scene. This indicates that autonomy will only be feasible if there are self-representatives who express specific interests and have the representation base, which is not currently available in the existing elites.

Autonomy is the outcome of negotiations or an initiative, not an agreement, and thus carries two interpretations: Approval or rejection. The readiness of the Sahrawi elites to apply the initiative directly on the ground without a transitional phase, which should not exceed two years (Saleh,2012).

But it is important to develop a Strategy to change the positions and support the reverse tension forces to become supporting forces. And here lies success, based on the Pyramid Model, which is used to determine the levels of parties or actors in society or the system.

When we know the structure, we can develop a strategy to control and influence the parties that are against the peace agreement between the parties to the conflict, where we build campaigns through which we can take action aimed at changing policies, positions or programs for any type of institution, and to adopt the idea of "pushing towards the activation of expanded autonomy" as an integrated political solution far from the framework of initiatives and finding elites capable of implementing and implementing the proposed solution and changing society by paying attention to the issue and directing decision makers to the solution without hesitation and waiting because it would create new spaces that are difficult to solve in light of the accelerated changes in the region.

Working with others, individuals and human rights organizations to bring about change, and may include specific and short-term activities to reach a long-term vision for change (Al-Hamdani,2013).

But on the issue of the conflict and after reaching a peace agreement and identifying the opposition in the field of reverse tension forces and their size, the question remains whether the goal is achievable with the presence of an opposition?

The strategy of change is the work of propaganda campaigns and popular pressure from public opinion and organizations concerned with human rights, health and development ... Etc. on the political base at the middle level, and therefore the grassroots base will be influenced in a mutual way and the impact on the political leadership, and also through the communication of

the international community, internal organizations will become with the organizations of the international community. There will be coalitions with international organizations that put pressure on political leadership to make a decision on the conflict, and the United Nations is the pressure on the political leadership "Morocco, Polisario, Algeria" to activate the proposal and urgency to reach a political solution because there is a possibility of extending the mission for another year to give more opportunities to negotiate and reach a common base, or to transfer the conflict from Chapter VI, which provides for a solution by mutual consent to Chapter VII, which states Imposing the solution (Saleh,2012).

Because of the difficulty and complexities of the conflict, the imposition is impossible to be a referendum, but one of the proposals such as the autonomy proposal. The counterparties can be influenced by convincing the opposition parties and lobbies that the solution to the conflict will work on the existence of a democratic incubator that allows everyone to participate.

Therefore, these forces will think of partisan and political pluralism that enables them to reach representation of the power in a wider base than before, and convince Israel through the strategy of threatening Israeli national security in the growth environment of extremist movements that tamper with the security of the Middle East.

It is not in their interest to have a new environment for the growth of ISIS and some movements. As for the WSRW lobby, it is possible to make a coalition with it to be the permanent observer of resource exploration in the region, even under autonomy to maintain a certain policy. To invest in the wealth of the region.

CONCLUSION

From the above and through an in-depth study of the conflict in terms of its evolving stages and turning points, several key conclusions have been reached, the most prominent of which are:

- It has been proven that resolving the conflict cannot be achieved without consensus among the political leaders involved—namely, Morocco, the Polisario, and Algeria. We infer that bridging the perspectives between Morocco and Algeria is fundamental, as in my view, the Polisario is merely a proxy for Algeria in this dispute.
- The optimal solution is expanded autonomy, which has led to a convergence of interests that was not an impractical solution, considering several factors influencing the bargaining context, including the time factor for decision-makers must be considered, as it reflects precise conflict management .
- A third party must have genuine direct interests with both sides and possess strong influence over them in some way.
- The regional context is essentially a political division that defines the roles of political conflicts. A state not geographically part of the region may be considered a direct member due to its political role. The effectiveness of the regional context factor is linked to the form and nature of prevailing bargains in the area.

- The optimal and least costly solution to the Sahara conflict is the autonomy project implemented independently with self-sufficient tools. In an article, he described it as recipes for failure and one for success.
- The balance of capabilities for each party, the balance of shared sensitivities (including differences in values), the balance of needs (seeking resources and capabilities from other states in the international system), the balance of internal perception, and the balance of risks (facing the consequences of gaining an advantage or avoiding a specific threat). Thus, autonomy is both an international and national context, albeit to varying degrees, especially as it remains open to future consensus among the conflicting parties.
- The international community's call for a political solution does not indicate its awareness of the deadlock reached or its denial of the history of political initiatives in the issue, including Morocco's acceptance of self-determination.

However, with active efforts to persuade African states to disengage from the Sahara issue, withdraw recognition, and gain Arab support internationally, Algeria will likely retreat from its position, as the cost would be too high under its current internal conditions.

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